

Turbulent Insights?

Lessons from the 2025 BWE Ambient Turbulence Round Robin

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Why Interlaboratory Comparisons Are Important (according to IEC 17025)

- Demonstrating comparability between accredited laboratories
- Reviewing and harmonizing procedures
- Quality assurance and continuous improvement
- Meeting accreditation requirements
- Strengthening confidence in reports and market transparency

In short:

Interlaboratory comparisons are the key instrument to ensure comparability, quality, and credibility in expert reporting practices.

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Overview

- Task dispatch: June 26, 2025
- Submission deadline: July 25, 2025
- 27 participants, 24 result submissions
- Results evaluation sent: November
- Evaluation team:
 - Danny Rimpel (Deutsche WindGuard)
 - Katja Hofer (TÜV SÜD)
 - Martin Richter-Rose (PAVANA)
 - Maximilian Kilburg (ABO Energy)

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Task Description

- Location: Barnstädt – Wind distribution at 141.5 m
- Roughness and elevation model provided
EMD-Corine-based roughness lines and DGM5 contour lines in WAsP format

Requested Results:

- Sectorial and wind-speed-dependent ambient turbulence
- Sectorial and wind-speed-dependent standard deviation of ambient turbulence
- Sectorial and wind-speed-dependent representative ambient turbulence
- Roughness lengths at 3 locations near the calculation point
- Information on the models used

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The Location

- Barnstädt, Saalekreis, Saxony-Anhalt
- Wind distribution at 141.5 m
- Red circle with a 5 km radius
- Flat site with open agricultural fields
- Undisturbed inflow

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Results: Roughness and Elevation Model

- The provided roughness model was used 10 times
- The provided elevation model was used 14 times

Roughness values at reference locations

Point	CLC roughness length [m]	Mean[m]	Range [m]	Description
1	0,056	0,063	0,03 – 0,15	North: Open terrain with scattered vegetation
2	0,400	0,386	0,06 – 1,00	West: Transition to denser vegetation / edge of settlement
3	0,100	0,090	0,004 – 0,40	South: Agricultural land

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Used Software	Software	Variant	Amount
	Wakeguard	-	2
		adjusted basis due to new insights	1
	wake2e	-	2
	windPRO Site Compliance	WEng	3
		WAsP	2
		WEng/WAsP	3
		Downscaling	1
		WAsP + in-house procedure	1
	meteodyn	-	1
		internal turbulence adjustment	1
	In-house procedure	-	1
		LES Simulation	1
	WindStation CFD		1
	UL Openwind		1
	Ewind (CFD)		1
	WRF		1

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Comparison with Measurement*
shows that model results mostly **overestimate** ambient turbulence.

*Measurement not shown

Excursus – The Belly

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Profiles can be grouped into 3 categories

1. IEC
2. Constant
3. The Belly

Mean Ambient Turbulence

Excursus – The Belly

The course of mean ambient turbulence does not always follow the IEC curve

Common case in Germany

Reason:

In the mid-range wind speed region, the proportion of stable stratification is higher than in the IEC world (where neutral stratification dominates).

This is driven by:

- Weather patterns (temperate westerly zone)
- Solar radiation
- Surface roughness

Stable stratification suppresses turbulence

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Mean Representative Turbulence Intensity

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Comparison with Measurement* shows that model results mostly **overestimate** representative turbulence intensity.

*Measurement not shown

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Key Message

- High consistency with identical inputs and boundary conditions
- Consistent trends across all wind speeds; variation within expected range
- Tends to be conservative compared to measurements (modeled values slightly higher)

Three result clusters:

- **IEC-oriented:** Turbulence decreases with increasing wind speed
- **Constant:** Nearly constant level across the entire range
- **Empirical:** Combination of the two approaches above, with a local minimum (“dip”) at medium wind speeds

→ All three approaches represent different modeling philosophies but are methodologically plausible.

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Interpretation, Limitations, and Benefits

- **Convergence at high wind speeds:** The range of results decreases significantly
- **Scope:** Ambient turbulence = terrain/roughness; no wake turbulence included
→ **No direct derivation for load or structural safety verification (effective turbulence intensity)**

Practical benefits:

- Confirms methodological quality and comparability among assessors
- Provides a data basis for harmonization and further development of uniform standards

Thank you for your attention!

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